

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Standard Operating Procedures

Technical Documentation

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Versions

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1 Introduction

Top predator surveys can be used to investigate the abundance and distribution of birds and marine mammals. Our final aim is to provide estimates of total prey consumption needs (prey biomass, energy, carbon) of the whole community of warm-blooded top predators (marine mammals, birds) to be able to make a direct spatial/temporal comparison with abundance and distribution of zooplankton and nekton, local ocean and sea ice productivity, abundance of litter, frontal systems etc. Top predator surveys can be conducted from the ship or the helicopter.

That means:

ALL Birds + Mammals + other life (turtles, large fish, seaweed) and pollution are CONTINUOUSLY surveyed

Participation in interdisciplinary cruises often mean that there is limited capacity to perform surveys, and censuses are done by one or few observers. The consequence of this is that different census methods must be combined by a single surveyor.

Text Box 1: Material ship-based surveys:

Observation posts on central front Peildeck: 2 Birdboxes with

- Hood, ropes for fixing hood, floor, rubber mats, beams for floor variation, foot support lift-cables
- Additional wooden shields for wind protection along railings to the sides of obs posts
- Alu boxes (3) with building tools /nuts etc, heater, power-line, angle board, etc etc

To bring daily for observation:

- Radio/mariphone
- Standard binocular, + evtl. laser binocular for distance measurements
- Heinemann ruler and angle board
- GPS
- Alarm clocks snapshot and 10 min intervals
- Multomap with birdobs forms and codata forms
- Multomap to safely store completed forms
- Identification guide(s)

Figure xx: Left: the SUIT nets are hoisted up to enable net rinsing during hauling in. Right: cod end are retrieved after net rinsing to be transported to the wet lab for processing the catch (© Jan Andries van Franeker).

2 Methods: surveying from the ship

Top predators are counted from the Peildeck (above the bridge) using specially adapted boxes. These boxes are installed centrally on the deck (eye height 21.8 m) and offer shelter from the weather and provide a good overview of the water surface and air within the transect (see Text Box 1). The outside position is preferred to the bridge itself, as it offers unrestricted views, a clearer picture (especially when using binoculars) and sound by less conspicuous wildlife can aid detection (Van Franeker 1994). Due to the usually restricted capacities on board, only one surveyor at the time is actually counting (in contrast to the ESAS guidelines where two persons per side are recommended). Surveys are conducted when the ship is moving (8-15 kn) and when daylight is considered sufficient to detect and identify marine top predators.

Top predators are counted within blocks of ten minutes (these time blocks are later associated with the ships' position and abiotic parameters). Records are noted on a paper form (BIRDOBS) with pencil. All field descriptions on this forms can be found in Annex 1. Parallely, environmental and ship parameters are noted for the same 10 minute block on another paper form (CODATA). For more details on forms see **Text Box 2**. All field descriptions on this forms can be found in Annex 2. Data should be entered in excel as soon as possible after the count (to avoid/correct possible mistakes).

In general, top predators are counted in line with the 'European Seabird At Sea' (ESAS) guidelines for birds and line transect for marine mammals. Densities are calculated for both stationary and snapshot birds/marine mammals per surveyed surface area.

If circumstances allow, a 300 m band transect (150 m on both sides of the ship) in a 180° forward quadrant and 300 m ahead is surveyed by a single observer from the observation box. Important reasons to view both sides are:

- a) gives much better opportunities to keep control of ship-associated birds that continuously circle the ship, and
- b) in most viewing conditions, many smaller bird species or penguin heads are hard to detect at greater distances than 150 m.

However a standard transect band assumes that one is crossing a uniform habitat, which often is not the case, due to either the habitat or the chosen track by the ship. **When needed, the transect band should be modified in such a way that the survey results remain representative for the habitat one is crossing.** Some examples:

Disturbing glare: if too much glare is preventing proper observations in the standard transect band, one could switch to a smaller width at the glare side, e.g. 100 m and a wider

band, e.g. 200 m at the non-glare side. Two-sided observations remain to be preferred, only switch to one side when the glare side makes data recording impossible.

Ship follows leads in the ice: Birds tend to concentrate along leads, so densities around the lead differ from those over bordering large ice flows. Transect width to both sides should be chosen such that the survey results reflect the overall habitat. That means that in leads through dense ice, the transect width should include about half of the bordering icefloes. For example, if floes alongside the lead are estimated at an average size of 500 m, the transect band must be chosen at 250 m to both sides. The similar approach should be chosen when cruising parallel with the ice edge.

Ship avoids icebergs: Icebergs may hold large concentrations of resting birds (or sometimes seals), but the ship avoids bergs at certainly greater distances than 150 m. Do NOT change your standard transect width, but record visible concentrations on icebergs with the association BER, tick them as TC=1 and give distance in column DI. In analyses, correct the number of animals proportional to the transect band used. Checking Icebergs for bird concentrations is the only case in which you can use binoculars.

Perfect observation conditions: If conditions for viewing and detecting are absolutely perfect, e.g., with good light from behind and a mirror flat sea surface, and not many animals around, you can consider widening the transect to e.g. 200 m or even 300 m to each side. The distance chosen should match with what you consider the distance that you will discover ALL sizes of flying birds or penguins sticking head out of the water.

Unusual sightings outside the survey or transect (e.g. unusual numbers, species, etc.) can provide valuable insights in distribution ranges of rare species (e.g., Fey et al. 2025). Observations can be recorded but should be marked as out of transect count (OUT/UIT). Always add a CODA entry as accompanying information!

2.1 Seabirds

Observations are made with bare eyes, binoculars can be used to confirm species identity and to identify additional details on age or plumage. All birds in or on the water surface within the transect are identified and counted continuously as 'in transect scan (TC)'. The band width at moment of detection should be noted. To avoid overestimates of flying birds, snapshot counts are used, as proposed by Tasker (1984). This means that flying birds are only counted as 'in transect scan (TC)' when within the transect at a certain snapshot moment (usually each minute, depending on ship speed the snapshot can be extended or shortened). Birds associated with the ship (attracted by it) are identified and counted but are noted as 'ship associated (SA)'. They are counted once for one 10 minute block. This to

avoid overestimation of birds in a certain area, that would not have been there without the presence of the ship. For each observation the location of the bird is noted (flying, in/on water, on ice). If a bird is observed actively feeding the 'Feed' box should be ticked on the form. In addition, information on associations can be added, such as associations to other ships in the surrounding, associated to prey or other top predators, associated to multi species flocks, etc.). Details on moult, age or plumage can be described. Additional information or details should be noted as well. Seabirds on icebergs beyond 150 m can be registered with the association BER (iceberg). Tick TC and add perpendicular distance. Descriptions of all available fields on the form are given in the Annex.

2.2 Marine Mammals

To record marine mammals, the line-transect method is applied (Hiby & Hammond 1989). In the past, seals have been counted using band-transect methods, but since 2020 a switch to line-transect was made. This means that all marine mammals are recorded when observed, regardless their location. Remember that only bare eye's detections are considered and that the focus should always be on the transect. Do not worry about 'missing' whales. The low chance of detection out of transect is corrected during the analysis later (Rdistance). Do NOT scan the surroundings with your binocular: if you happen to pick up a mammal when using the binocular, put the binocular aside and check/evaluate if you would have detected this animal without the binocular. If unaided detection is or seems unlikely, do NOT record the observation on your forms.

In addition to species, count and activity, please always note (Gaskin 1982; Van Franeker 1992):

the exact time (minute GMT),

the ANGLE (in relation to the ships direction) and

the angular distance (ADIS).

Tick TC (TC=1; and give band distance within transect) when marine mammal is first found in transect, do this to compare data with earlier band-transect methods. The distance is measured with a range finder based on the Heinemann rules (Heinemann 1981). Bow riders are counted once. If they stay for more than 10 minutes they can be entered again but then as 'ship-associated (SA)'.

2.3 Other (seaweed, fish, litter, ships, etc.) are recorded as in band-transect:

Within transect note TC=1 and enter the distance category (DI). Leave TC blank for anything outside the chosen transect.

2.4 Some Priorities:

Always maintain focus on the narrow band-transect even when, or especially when(!) densities are low and boring. Depending on conditions, the transect width is in principle 300 m, 150 to both sides (divided in A 0-50 m B 50-100 m C 100-150 m). The assumption of chosen transect width = we expect to see ALL within the transect band, and need no correction for distances (as e.g. applied in SAS observations)). Forward distance is in principle 300 m; for birds in flight depending on ship speed and snapshot frequency chosen. An accepted (!) side effect of our focus on the forward band transect block is low detectability for animals recorded by line-transect methods a bit further out, and thus rapidly decreasing detection curves.

Within our aim of overall prey-consumption estimates, please do NOT waste time/energy on rare sightings, hard to identify species, distant sightings, an 'over-accurate' number of animals in groups. Such efforts reduce the accuracy of our consumption data. Do NOT spend time trying to identify that distant maybe rare 'large whale', or to decide if something is e.g. a Northern or Southern Giant Petrel, or a nice photo of that beautiful bird. This is hard and maybe less fun, but it is essential for consistent and reliable data collection and consequently prey consumption estimates!

While at work, do not try to be social with fellow passengers: it reduces your concentration: so, do NOT allow fellow passengers in the (second) bird box while you are doing observations; ask people sheltering outside next to your box to be quiet and not ask for your attention!

Text Box 2: Forms and Data

The ship based top-predator surveys are based on 10 minute time-blocks and require multiple forms and data files to be maintained. Forms are:

- VOYAGE MASTER CARD containing general data valid for the whole voyage, like ship size, observers position/height, equipment, etc.
- CODATA-FORM giving general ships and environmental data like ice-conditions, observation-type and parameters for each 10 minute period or other observation unit
- BIRD RECORD FORM for recording bird(and mammal) observations.

The paper forms need to be made unique by always filling out the header with Voyage, Observer, and form type and number.

During a cruise each observer needs to number his/her forms **consecutively**. Note: datasets from codata and bird forms have to be linked by voyage-name/nr plus observers name with the date and time in GMT. **EACH 10 minute period MUST have an entry on EACH of these forms** even if no birds were observed at all. In that case the bird form should mention the GMT with 'NUL' in the species column. On the codata many 10min time-blocks may have same info, but still each MUST be entered on the codata form.

A final data source needed for the analysis are data-tables derived from the ships computer system

- SHIPSDATA with time linked info on position, water depth, temperature salinity etc. (mostly averaged for 10 mns).

Note: in principle, the written observational data should be computerized in files above EVERY DAY. It alerts you to errors or omissions in the hand-written forms (in which memory will often still help to correct) avoiding these in later days. It also ensures that data is backed-up. Computer work may mean that you have to reduce the number of actual possible surveys to be able to keep up. Once computerized, ensure that the paper forms are stored in an organized manner, ensuring anyone can find his/her way for later checks of details.

3 Methods: surveying from the helicopter

Top predator surveys from the helicopter are complementary to the ship-based top predator surveys. Heli surveys broaden spatial coverage in especially the sea-ice where the ship is limited in its movements by heavy ice and often deviates from the strict linear transects needed for unbiased survey data. Like the ship-based surveys, helicopter observations aim to provide quantitative data on the whole community of warm-blooded top predators, that is all seabirds including penguins, seals and whales combined. Such broad aims translate into a relatively simple but very strict observation method that differs from e.g., dedicated seal- or whale survey flight methods that helicopter crews or ships officers might be familiar with from other research groups. It is also different from the described ship-based observations

that contain a lot of details for variations on the basic methodologies. Due to the speed of flight of the helicopters (60-80 knots, 300 feet altitude) and possibility of flying straight lines at all times (not following leads, no need to deviate for icebergs) the methods must and can be very basic and simple:

Basic elements of helicopter methods are:

- Constant flight altitude **300 feet**
- Constant flight speed at **60 to max 80 knots**
- Spatial sub-divisioning of transect based on **GPS waypoints**
- Fly **straight lines** irrespective of the habitat

A strict band-transect method for all animal groups is conducted by the front seat observer. No line transect data or details of animals outside the transect band are recorded. From outside the transect band, only rare species or unusual numbers are noted with note 'outside'. Environmental data and timing of waypoints are recorded by a back seat co-observer. This observer should also only make notes of exceptional species observed to the side.

3.1 Detailed methods

- **Survey flight time preferences:** preferably around midday. Besides optimal light conditions it may be relevant in relation to haul-out times of seals. For this reason and potential observer fatigue, flights should be restricted to max. 2 per day.
- **Seats:** Two observers are required. One in the front (co-pilot seat) as main observer, one behind the observer (sea-ice and time observer). Under certain circumstances a third observer seat may be necessary for, e.g., calibration or training. Preferably no other persons should join the flight as it is extremely distracting. If an additional person is onboard he/she should be notified to restrict (hectic) movement and communication to the minimum. This person should not notify additional sightings.
- **Calibration flight:** In order to calibrate the observers sense of distance within transect at the start of EVERY flight, the pilot is asked to make two perpendicular overflights of the bow of Polarstern (118 m) at the standard altitude (300 m) and speed (60 kn), using the ship to calibrate viewing distances, once to the left and once to the right of the observers.
- **Flight track design:** In principle a predesigned straight rectangular transect should be provided by the observers, consisting of two parallel long legs of ~40 nm (used to be 60 nm, but for safety reasons the pilots asked for shorter legs), with in-between short crossings of about 6 nm (on which no counts are conducted).

- **Constant standard flight mode:** For an unbiased sampling, it should be emphasized that standard flight modes are maintained at all times, so not following leads or wildlife assemblies etc.
- **Intermediate stops:** Observation may need to be temporarily stopped for several reasons. This could be technical-related to assure safe flights, requested by the pilot. Sometimes, observers may request a stop to have a closer look somewhere, e.g., to count a larger group or identify an animal to species level. This is obviously in good consultation with the pilot regarding flight safety. To deviate from the trackline, an additional waypoint should be made at the beginning and the end of such stop. The trackline should be restarted at the same point where the regular survey stopped.
- **Pilot observation assistance:** The broad observation goals imply that what the front observer detects is just a minimum estimate of animal abundance within the transect. He/she will report sightings on the intercom. If the co-observer or the pilot have the impression that certain animals within(!) the transect are missed, please report on intercom.

3.2 Information for main observer

3.2.1 Before flight:

- Familiarize yourself with working with the spreadsheet page designed to plan a flight track and forwarding hardcopy prints of that track to pilots and bridge. Between decision to fly and time of departure you usually have little time and you must be able to do it fast!
- Don't forget the initial two perpendicular distance calibration flights (at 300 ft altitude; standard 60 knot speed) over bow or stern of ship (both flights over either bow or stern to assure you view the 118 m long Polarstern once to your left, once to your right). Use elements inside the helicopter to assist you in remembering the approximate borders of your band transect. But remember that such points are not always valid e.g. because of the helicopter flying in an angle to its trackline due to strong wind.
- From the 300 ft altitude an e.g. 250 m wide transect (\pm a 'ships length' to left and a ships length to right) seems really narrow. But resist the thought of going much wider, usually around 300 m (150 to each side) is the limit, maybe in excellent conditions (perfect light, smooth ice, low predator densities; great pilot) go to 400 m. If really needed, you can change transect width during the flight if properly noted, and if co-observer is clearly informed.
- Check flight speed regularly, as wind and other conditions can change, and remind pilot if necessary. Both front and rear observers should track on their GPS if altitude and speed are kept by the pilot.

- Ensure that you are familiar and trained in the GPS procedures including its coordination with the ice-observer on Waypoint numbering, setting ± 2 min waypoints, how to act when Waypoint errors occur etc.. During the flight you have no time!

3.2.2 Once counting:

- Force yourself to concentrate on the rather nearby sector of the band transect (no more than a few hundred meters ahead). The rapid movement makes nearby observations very tiring on your eyes, but it is needed! Resist a focus on the far horizon distance which is far more relaxing.
- Resist the tendency to make (too many) notes on animals seen outside your band transect. Also tell pilot and co-observer that your interest in such outside animals is very limited (in contrast to animals within the transect band that they think you are missing).
- Make notes on ice conditions at the end of a waypoint stretch only if you have time and if they seem relevant in comparison to the 'single side' conditions recorded by the second observer in the back.
- Accurate species records are not the holy grail. Only interrupt the actual survey for essential controls (e.g. group size in large number of animals in water) or absolute unique observations (the Arnoux's beaked whale you always wanted to see and take pictures/film of).
- Please make photo/film ONLY during non-counting stretches (e.g. radio stops, the connecting flight between the transects, and when returning to ship after counts have stopped etc.).
- The data to be filled in on the observation form are similar to those in ship-based observations

3.3 Information for GPS/ice observer

3.3.1 Before flight:

- Familiarize yourself with using GPS (waypoints and tracking). Know how to quickly return to the required screen if battery-problems occur or wrong buttons were pushed. Good waypoints are the backbone of the helicopter counts! Train yourself using the waypoint system in coordination with the main observer. Once in the air you have no time for lengthy discussions.

- Familiarize yourself with estimating ice-surfaces and their classification as floe or new ice.
- Be aware that this is not a tourist job: during counts you have NO time for e.g. photos (wait for radio stops or short inter transect flights).

3.3.2 GPS Waypoints procedures:

- Make first waypoint nr 001 at helideck before departure - fill in on form.
- Make second waypoint nr 002 at lift-off - fill in on form.
- After transect-calibration by the observer in the front, wait for his request to make first waypoint nr 003 to actually start the count. Wait for front observer to repeat the number and to say NOW. At "NOW" the waypoint should actually be entered on GPS and entered on form with the time.

Then, at about every 2 mins after: warn front seat observer that it is time to prepare a new waypoint, naming the waypoint number that according to you has to follow: 'Prepare Waypoint xxx'

- Wait for front observer to repeat the number and to say NOW.
- At "NOW" the Waypoint should actually be entered on GPS and entered on form.
- Continue 2-mins Waypoints until front observer asks waypoint to end or interrupt the count.

3.3.3 2 minute ice observations

During counts, in between all waypoints, make quick estimates of ice cover within the transect band as (1-4 should add up to 100%):

1. % open water (really open, so not slush, brash etc. which go under young ice).
2. % young ice (e.g., thin flexible film dark ice, to whitish young ice, nilas, loose new small pancakes).
3. % floes (solid often angular floes, thick and with full snow cover).
4. % old (brash type).
5. Number of icebergs (= rough indication of number of bergs on your side of transect, within distance of ± 1000 m)

- Note under notes, when you have time, rough estimate of floe size (e.g., class <10 m; 10-100 m; 100-1000 m; >1000 m); remarkable animals e.g. whales or large groups of seals at greater distance (>100 m) from your side.

After return: immediately download track and waypoint data from the two GPS's to your laptop, make back-ups, and then clean the memories of both GPS's to have them ready for the next flight (starting again at waypoint 001).

4 References

Feij B, Kühn S, Meijboom A, Van Franeker JA, Bornemann H, Kelly N, Schaafsma FL (2025). Distribution of Arnoux's beaked whales (*Berardius arnuxii*). *Marine Mammal Science* 41(1): e13158. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mms.13158>

Gaskin DE (1982) *The ecology of whales and dolphins*. Heinemann, London, pp 282-288

Heinemann D (1981) A range finder for pelagic bird censusing. *J. Wildl Manage* 45:489-493.

Hiby AR, Hammond PS (1989). Survey techniques for estimating abundance of cetaceans. *Rep. Int. Whal. Commn. (Special Issue 11)*: 47-80.

SCAR-GSS (1996) Report of the 1996 APIS Survey Design and Implementation Workshop. APIS Report No. 2. SCAR Group of Specialists on Seals. Workshop at the British Antarctic Survey, July 29-31, Cambridge, UK. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371722039>

Tasker ML, Hope Jones P, Dixon T, Blake BF (1984). Counting seabirds at sea from ships: a review of methods employed and a suggestion for a standardized approach. *Auk* 101: 567-577.

Van Franeker JA (1992). Top predators as indicators for ecosystem events in the confluence zone and marginal ice zone of the Weddell and Scotia seas, Antarctica, November 1988 to January 1989 (EPOS Leg 2). *Polar Biology* 12: 93-102.

Van Franeker JA (1994). A comparison of methods for counting seabirds at sea in the Southern Ocean. *Journal of Field Ornithology* 65(1): 96-108

5 Annex

- Field description BIRDOBS
- Field description CODATA
- Protocols